

Trial Development the Evaluation Method of Quantification the Feeling of Preventing Visibility by Front A Pillar

Authors : Toshiya Arakawa and Hideki Sato

Abstract : There are many drivers who feel right A pillar of Japanese right-hand-drive car preventing visibility on turning right or left at intersection. On the other hand, there is a report that almost pedestrian accident is caused by the delay of finding pedestrian by drivers and this is found by drivers' eye movement. Thus, we developed the evaluation method of quantification using drivers' eye movement data by least squares estimation and we applied this method to commercial vehicle and evaluation the visibility. It is suggested that visibility of vehicle can be quantified and estimated by linear model obtained from experimental eye fixation data and information of vehicle dimensions.

Keywords : eye fixation, modeling, obstacle feeling, right A pillar.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014